

Susceptibility of promising rice cultivars to whitebacked planthopper

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The whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*, previously a minor rice pest, is becoming a threat at the crop's early tillering stage with the introduction of high yielding varieties and high-input technology. Thirty-nine rice cultivars (see table) were evaluated against WBPH attack in the field in 1977 kharif. The rices were transplanted in two advanced trials in the last week of June in a completely randomized block experiment with three replicates. The pest population on 15 hills/replication was recorded in the last week of August when pest incidence was at its peak. RP633-519-1-3-4-1 harbored the lowest population (6.5) and IR36 the next lowest (8.5). The maximum infestation was on Prasad (47.3). No cultivar was immune to WBPH attack. Rasi (IET1444), which was planted in an agronomic trial, suffered heavily; it had 400 to 500 insects/hill or more. ■

Whitebacked planthopper populations on promising rice cultivars. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Designation	Av population (no./hill)
<i>Medium duration</i>	
RP6-516-31-4	34.4
UPR103-44-1-1-1-1-2	32.5
Jaya	32.3
UPRI 73-23	38.8
CR75-93	29.4
CR167-10	28.3
BG90-2	26.9
IR2153-26-3-5-2	25.9
UPR84-30-1-2-1-3	25.2
UPR70x30-4-1	24.2
CR164-12	24.1
UPRI 73-18	22.7
IR2151-190-3-5	22.5
CR94-MR 1550	21.3
CR129-118	21.0
UPR243-247-1	20.6
RP632-94-1-2-1-7	16.1
BG35-2	15.9
S52134	15.6
TC-A-1-P2-5-2	15.3
BR 34-13-5	15.1
IR36	8.5
RP633-519-1-3-4-1	6.5
C.D. at 5%	11.85

Designation	(no./hill)
<i>Early duration</i>	
Prasad	47.3
UPR103D-7-1	37.7
Pusa 33	35.6
UPRI75-4	33.0
CR142-3-2	31.9
UPR221-124-1	31.6
UPR103-80-1-2-1-2	31.0
UPR83D-8-1	31.0
UPR4D-1-3-1	29.3
OR34-16	23.4
UPR190D-17-1	22.0
Pusa 2-21	22.0
UPR4D-1-1	17.7
IR2061-487-1-19	17.4
UPR82-1-7	13.2
RP1158-85-1	12.1
CD at 5%	10.99

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deepwater

Screening deepwater rice varieties in different water regimes

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Twenty-five deepwater rice varieties, along with Pankaj, were screened for elongation capacity, nodal differentiation,

and internode elongation in two sets of experiments. In the first set, 30-day-old potted seedlings were suspended in a water column 80 cm deep in cement tanks (Photo 1). In the other set the seeds were germinated in a 40-cm water column in glass jars in the laboratory (Photo 2). One set of potted plants was also grown under normal conditions.

1. Cement tank used in screening deepwater rices. CRR, Cuttack, India.

Temperature tolerance

2. Glass jars used in screening deepwater rices. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Nageribao, Habiganj DW2, and Molladigha grew and elongated to the surface of the 80-cm water column in 24 hours. They elongated fastest. Nhok Nhounh and Khao Gaew reached the surface in 36 to 48 hours. Pankaj did not reach the water level and it died. Elongation of the leaf sheaths and, in a few varieties, of the internodes caused the growth that enabled varieties to reach the water surface. In the glass jars as in the cement tank Nageribao, Sampatti, Habiganj DW2, and Molladigha grew relatively faster than the other varieties. Pankaj did not elongate beyond 15 cm.

Internode differentiation and elongation occurred earliest in Nageribao – 30 days after germination. Aswina 322, Habiganj DW1, Habiganj DW2, Sampatti, and Molladigha took 40 days; the other varieties, 50 to 60 days. In Jalmagna, a popular deepwater variety from Uttar Pradesh, internodal differentiation took place 50 days after germination. Nodal rooting was profuse and nodal tillering high in Nageribao, followed by Habiganj DW2, Sampatti, and Molladigha. Good segregants from crosses involving Nageribao can be obtained at CRRI.

The seed of 23 deepwater varieties were received from IRRI. Nageribao (from Assam), Jalmagna, and Pankaj were obtained locally. ■

Two extremely cool-tolerant varieties

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In 1976, IRRI selected 6 cool-tolerant indica rice varieties from 12,200 entries of the germplasm bank on the basis of growth duration, plant height, spikelet sterility, leaf color, and anthesis. The cool tolerance of the six varieties at booting stage was rechecked in the phytotron of the HNAES.

The materials tested were the six indicas and three japonicas found to be cool-tolerant in Japan. The indicas were Leng Kwang, Thangone, C-21, Silewah, Pratao, and Dourado Agulha; the japonicas were Somewake, Sorachi, and Hayayuki. Twenty seeds were sown in a circular pattern in a 4-liter plastic pot. The plants were grown at 26°/20°C

day/night temperature in an artificial light room for 12 hours at an intensity of 27.6 klux.

Auricle distance was used as a criterion to show the panicle developmental stage at the beginning of cooling. Plants at different panicle developmental stages were cooled at 12°C for 4 consecutive days in the natural light room. After the treatment, the plants were returned to the artificial-light room. At maturity, spikelet fertility was determined for panicles of main stems grouped by auricle distance.

Cool tolerance was highest in Leng Kwang and Silewah, and intermediate in Thangone and C-21 (see figure). The latter two indica varieties had about the same cool tolerance as the three japonicas. Pratao and Dourado Agulha, which were highly cool tolerant in the IRRI test (15°C), were susceptible in this test (12°C).

Results at IRRI and at HNAES showed

Fertility of spikelets in rice plants subjected to cool temperature (12°C for 4 days) at different panicle developmental stages indicated by auricle distance of –5 to +10 cm. Hokkaido Experiment Station, Japan.